
THE INFLUENCE OF ADVERSITY INTELLIGENCE ON ACADEMIC RESILIENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study investigated adversity intelligence and self-esteem as correlates of academic adjustment among Senior Secondary School Students in the Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. The research employed a correlational design and was guided by six research questions and six hypotheses. The population consisted of 41,602 senior secondary school students, from whom a sample of 350 students was selected using both stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Data collection was carried out using a self-developed questionnaire titled “Adversity Intelligence, Self-Esteem and Academic Adjustment Questionnaire” (AISEAAQ). The instrument was divided into two sections: Part A captured demographic data (school name, gender, class level), Part B comprised three sub-scales assessing Adversity Intelligence (AI), Self-Esteem (SE), and Academic Adjustment (AA). The instrument was validated by the researcher’s supervisor and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. Reliability was determined using Cronbach Alpha, based on responses from 40 non-sample students. The following reliability coefficients were obtained: AI ($\alpha = 0.85$), SE ($\alpha = 0.88$), and AA ($\alpha = 0.88$), indicating strong internal consistency. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed significant positive relationships between: Adversity awareness and academic adjustment, Adversity management and academic adjustment, and Self-awareness, self-image, self-acceptance, self-respect and academic adjustment among senior secondary school students. The study recommended that parents and teachers should guide students to become more self-aware and better manage their school environment. Emphasis was also placed on building students’ self-image to reduce vulnerability to negative peer pressure and promote academic success. Additionally, school counsellors were urged to support the development of students’ self-esteem to enhance their ability to navigate adversity and improve academic adjustment.

Keywords: Adversity Intelligence, Academic Resilience, Coping Strategies, Stress Management, Academic Performance

1. Introduction

The educational experience of secondary school students is shaped not only by intellectual ability but also by their capacity to withstand and navigate adversity. Students face a wide range of challenges, from academic pressure, peer conflicts, and family instability to economic hardship and environmental stressors. These issues demand emotional strength and psychological adaptability. In this context, adversity intelligence (AQ) and academic resilience have emerged as key psychological constructs that enable students to remain focused and perform effectively despite difficulties.

Adversity Intelligence, or AQ, refers to an individual's capacity to respond to adverse situations productively and constructively (Stoltz, 1997). It reflects how people perceive, interpret, and react to challenges in ways that foster growth rather than defeat. Stoltz (1997) proposed the four CORE dimensions of AQ, Control, Ownership, Reach, and Endurance, which collectively determine how individuals manage hardship. Unlike IQ (Intelligence Quotient) or EQ (Emotional Intelligence), AQ predicts a person's capacity to persevere and succeed in the face of adversity.

Similarly, academic resilience is the ability of students to effectively manage setbacks, stress, and pressure within the academic environment (Martin & Marsh, 2006). It involves determination, adaptability, and motivation, attributes essential for academic success. Resilient students are often those who thrive despite risk factors such as poverty, limited parental support, or resource constraints (Waxman, Gray, & Padron, 2003).

The link between AQ and academic resilience lies in their shared emphasis on psychological adaptability and proactive coping. Students with high adversity intelligence are more likely to develop strong internal coping mechanisms, view challenges as manageable, and maintain commitment to their academic goals. Academic resilience can thus be seen as a behavioral manifestation of AQ. Those with stronger AQ often exhibit greater perseverance and academic success despite external challenges.

In Nigeria, and particularly in Rivers State, the educational landscape presents numerous adversities that continually test students' ability to cope. These include erratic electricity supply, inadequate infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, insecurity, peer pressure, cultism, and financial constraints. Such stressors affect not only academic performance but also students' emotional and social development. Yet, some students consistently excel despite these difficulties, suggesting that internal psychological resources like AQ and resilience significantly influence outcomes (Ojo & Olaniyan, 2008).

Secondary school students, especially adolescents, are in a critical stage of development. They face academic expectations alongside identity formation, social influences, and the need for independence. Unfortunately, many academic interventions in Nigeria focus primarily on cognitive development while neglecting emotional and psychological adaptability. There is a pressing need to understand how constructs like adversity intelligence influence students' academic behavior and outcomes, particularly to design holistic interventions that go beyond the classroom.

A growing body of international research highlights the role of psychological factors in educational achievement. Martin and Marsh (2006) found that students with higher resilience tend to perform better, especially under stress. Stoltz (2000) suggested that AQ may even be a stronger predictor of long-term success than IQ. In the Nigerian context, studies by Adeyemo (2007) and Ofole and Okopi (2012) have explored emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and motivation as key influences on student outcomes. However, few studies have specifically examined the influence of adversity intelligence on academic resilience among Nigerian secondary school students.

This research gap underscores the need for more targeted interventions. Current resilience-based programs in Nigerian schools are often generalized, without considering individual students' varying capacities to handle adversity. Understanding the relationship between AQ and academic resilience can help schools design more effective psychological support systems, including AQ training to foster persistence, adaptability, and problem-solving.

Moreover, factors such as gender, school type (public vs. private), and socio-economic status are likely to moderate the relationship between AQ and academic resilience. For instance, Gartzia et al. (2012) found that females tend to demonstrate stronger emotional regulation and resilience. Likewise, private school students may benefit from more supportive learning environments, which could strengthen AQ and its impact.

This study is thus warranted to explore the influence of adversity intelligence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Rivers State. By identifying the degree to which AQ contributes to students' ability to handle academic and environmental challenges, the findings will offer practical insights for educators, school counselors, and policymakers. The ultimate aim is not just to enhance academic performance, but to equip students with the psychological tools needed to thrive both in and outside the school system.

As educational challenges in Nigeria grow more complex, the importance of psychological resilience and adversity management must not be overlooked. Focusing on these constructs may hold the key to improving student outcomes in a more sustainable and meaningful way. This study seeks to fill a critical research gap by empirically examining the influence of adversity intelligence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Comparative Studies and Global Contextualization

The relationship between adversity intelligence (AQ) and academic resilience has been examined across diverse cultural and educational settings, revealing both universal trends and region-specific nuances. Understanding how socio-cultural and educational systems shape AQ and resilience offers a framework for situating the Nigerian, particularly Rivers State, experience within a global context.

Western Contexts: In the United States and Australia, resilience and coping skills are key predictors of academic success. Martin and Marsh (2006), in a large-scale Australian study, linked academic resilience to motivational beliefs like self-efficacy, persistence, and planning, components aligned with Stoltz's (1997) CORE model of AQ: Control, Ownership, Reach, and Endurance. In the U.S., Masten (2001) described resilience as "ordinary magic," a common psychological resource that enables students to recover from stress and thrive academically. Socio-emotional learning programs integrated into curricula foster grit, emotional regulation, and problem-solving from an early age, skills closely related to AQ.

Asian Contexts: In East Asia, AQ and academic resilience are influenced by cultural values such as perseverance, respect for authority, and collective success. Liu et al. (2018) found that Chinese students with high AQ exhibited better emotional regulation and academic performance. In Japan, Morimoto et al. (2015) reported that mindfulness and cognitive restructuring enhanced resilience, reflecting a cultural focus on internal control and discipline. School programs in these regions promote mental toughness and emotional intelligence, supporting AQ development.

African Context: In Africa, AQ and resilience are shaped by poverty, social inequality, and cultural traditions. Theron (2016), in South Africa, found that community support, religious beliefs, and school engagement helped students withstand adversity. Nigerian studies have begun to explore related constructs. Ofole and Okopi (2012) examined emotional intelligence in visually impaired students in Ibadan, finding it buffered academic stress. Similarly, Adeyemo (2007) highlighted emotional intelligence and self-efficacy as crucial for academic success. However, empirical studies specifically on AQ in Nigerian schools remain limited, particularly among senior secondary school students.

Middle Eastern and Conflict Settings: In conflict-affected areas such as Palestine and Iraq, research focuses on resilience under extreme adversity. Thabet and Vostanis (2010) found that Palestinian adolescents with a strong internal locus of control, an AQ trait, demonstrated higher academic resilience despite trauma. Psychosocial school programs in such regions aim to build resilience and AQ.

Rivers State, Nigeria: Students in Rivers State confront multiple adversities, including poverty, cultism, unstable family structures, and infrastructural deficits. Despite these, many demonstrate academic resilience, suggesting the buffering role of AQ. However, most schools in the state lack structured programs to cultivate AQ. Nigeria's curriculum emphasizes cognitive outcomes over socio-emotional development, and cultural stigma around mental health impedes intervention. These gaps highlight the need for locally tailored strategies.

This study aims to empirically anchor the Nigerian experience within the global discourse on AQ and resilience. By integrating global insights with local realities, the research contributes to culturally relevant policy recommendations, curriculum reforms, and teacher training initiatives to support students' psychological readiness for academic success.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

Adversity Quotient (AQ) Theory – Paul G. Stoltz (1997)

Adversity Intelligence Theory, developed by Stoltz (1997), provides the primary theoretical anchor for this study. According to Stoltz, AQ refers to an individual's ability to respond to adversity in a productive and constructive manner. He posits that AQ is a better predictor of success than intelligence quotient (IQ), emotional intelligence (EQ), or education alone, especially in challenging or uncertain circumstances.

Stoltz's theory outlines four CORE dimensions of AQ:

- **Control:** The extent to which a person perceives they can influence a situation or outcome.
- **Ownership:** The degree to which a person holds themselves accountable for improving a situation.
- **Reach:** The perceived scope or spread of adversity across other areas of life.
- **Endurance:** The perception of how long the adversity or its impact will last.

These dimensions collectively shape how individuals handle adversity. In an academic setting, students with high AQ are likely to exhibit better focus, persistence, problem-solving, and emotional regulation, which are foundational for academic resilience. AQ thus informs students' motivational orientation, their coping mechanisms, and their capacity for sustained engagement in the face of academic setbacks.

Resilience Theory

Resilience Theory, derived from developmental psychology and popularized by scholars like Masten (2001) and Rutter (1987), provides a complementary perspective. Resilience is broadly defined as the ability to successfully adapt despite risk or adversity. In the academic context, resilience refers to students' ability to overcome learning difficulties, social stressors, or personal challenges and still achieve satisfactory educational outcomes.

Core assumptions of resilience theory include:

- Resilience is not a fixed trait but a dynamic process influenced by individual, familial, and environmental factors.
- Protective factors (e.g., supportive relationships, self-efficacy, emotional competence) mitigate the negative effects of risk factors.
- Resilience can be developed and strengthened through targeted interventions and positive environments.

This theory helps explain why some students thrive despite high-risk conditions, such as poverty, family dysfunction, or poor learning environments. Within this study, resilience theory provides insight into how adversity intelligence translates into observable academic behaviors and sustained performance.

Integration of Theories

The integration of AQ Theory and Resilience Theory provides a robust conceptual framework for understanding the relationship between students' psychological responses to adversity and their academic outcomes. AQ serves as the predictor or independent variable, influencing students' resilience, their adaptive outcome in the academic environment.

In this model:

- AQ (Control, Ownership, Reach, Endurance) → influences → Academic Resilience (persistence, adaptability, goal-directed behavior) → leads to → Positive academic outcomes

By applying these theories together, the study recognizes that:

- Adversity is a constant in the educational experience of Nigerian students.
- AQ determines how students appraise and manage these adversities.
- Resilience manifests as students' ability to bounce back, stay motivated, and succeed academically, despite setbacks.

Materials and Methods

The area of study is Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. Rivers East Senatorial district is one of the three senatorial districts in Rivers State, Nigeria. The district has a projected population of population of 2,670,903. It covers the following local government areas: Emohua, Etche, Ikwerre, Obio/Akpor, Ogu-Bolo, Okrika, Omuma and Port Harcourt. The Senatorial district is bound on the South by the Atlantic Ocean; to the North by Imo; to the East by Rivers South East Senatorial District and to the West by Rivers West Senatorial District. Its geographical coordinates are 4o 47' 21" North 6o 59' 55" East with a total area of 11,077km² (4,277mi²) (Wikipedia, 2020), and a latitude and longitude of 4.8581 and 6.9209

respectively. It is home to many indigenous ethnic groups: Ikwerre, Okirika, Etche etc. the inland part of the Senatorial district consists of tropical rainforest; towards the coast the typical Niger Delta environment features many mangrove swamps. The Senatorial District has a total of 351 public primary schools and 35 secondary schools. The secondary schools are more in local government area headquarters town and in Port Harcourt. This study adopted the correlational research design to investigate adversity intelligence and self-esteem as correlates of academic adjustment among senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. Correlational studies are research concerned with determining the relationship between two or more variables and also used in testing hypothesis of significance (Kpolovie, 2011; Ogidi, 2018). This study sought to find out the relationships among adversity intelligence, self-esteem and academic adjustment among senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. A total of 41,602 students from senior secondary schools in the study area (source: Senior Secondary School Board, Port Harcourt, 2023/2024) constituted the population of the study. The researcher decided to use public senior secondary school students because of the repeated challenges faced by students due to students-teacher relationship problems and issues within the school environment which are affecting students' academic adjustment. The sample of the study consisted of 400 students. Stratified sampling technique was used to select the sample size. The technique used involve dividing Rivers East Senatorial District into the various local government areas that make up senatorial district namely; Etche, Ikwerre, Emohua, Obio-Akpor, Omuma, Ogu-Bolo, Okrika, Oyigbo, and Port Harcourt City. Stratified random technique was used to draw 40 students from seven (7) Local Government areas while Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt City Local Government had 60 students each due to the population of senior secondary school students from the local government areas, this summed up to 400. Thus a total of 400 public senior secondary school students was drawn as sample for the study. The researcher developed an instrument that will aid data collection for the research titled "Adversity Intelligence, Self-Esteem and Academic Adjustment Inventory" (AISEAAI). The instrument consisted of two parts, A and B. Part A comprised information on demographic variables, such as gender, age and class while part B will be used to generate responses on Adversity Intelligence Inventory (AII), Self-Efficacy Inventory (SEI) and Academic Adjustment Inventory (AAI). The AII, SEI and AAI contained 15 items each designed to measure students' adversity intelligence, self-esteem and academic adjustment respectively. Items on the instruments are presented as statement to which respondents are requested to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on a 4-point modified Likert rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). Weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 point respectively. The content validity of the instrument was determined by the researcher's supervisor and two others in Measurement and Evaluation, all of the department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Their corrections and suggestions were reflected in the final version of the instrument. Hence, the instrument passed content validity adequate for the study. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Method. In doing this, the researcher administered 30 copies of the questionnaire to 30 senior secondary school students that were not part of the study area. The scores obtained were subjected to Cronbach Alpha statistics and the reliability indices are as follows: AII ($\alpha=0.85$), SEI ($\alpha=0.81$) and AAI ($\alpha=0.88$). The index for the AISEAAI is $\alpha=0.91$. The instrument was administered directly on the respondents by the researcher and three research assistants. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer all the research questions and to test the all hypotheses. The analysis of the hypotheses was tested

for statistical significance at 0.05 alpha level. The data collected was analyzed using statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Result

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

Table 1: PPMC Analysis (r) of the Relationship between Adversity Awareness and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

		Adversity Awareness	Academic Adjustment
Adversity Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.647**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Academic Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.647**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = 0.647$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Since the r-value is significant with $p < .05$, therefore the null hypothesis one is rejected. Hence, there is a significant positive relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result could mean that the more students are aware of adversity among students, the more their ability to adjust to their school environment and achieve higher academic performance.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

Table 2: PPMC Analysis (r) of the Relationship between Adversity Management and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

		Adversity Management	Academic Adjustment
Adversity Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.742**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Academic Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.742**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = 0.742$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Since the r -value is significant with $p < .05$, therefore the null hypothesis two is rejected. Hence, there is a significant positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result could mean that adversity management help them to adjust adequately in their school environment resulting to higher academic performance.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

Table 3: PPMC Analysis (r) of the Relationship between Self-Awareness and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

		Self-Awareness	Academic Adjustment
Self-Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.413
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.192
	N	400	400
Academic Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.413	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.192	
	N	400	400

****.** *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

Table 3 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .413$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Since the r -value is significant with $p > .05$, therefore the null hypothesis three is rejected. Hence, there is significant relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result could mean that the more students are aware of the reasons why they are in school, the more their academic adjustment.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

Table 4: PPMC Analysis (r) of the Relationship between Self-Image and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

		Self-Image	Academic Adjustment
Self-Image	Pearson Correlation	1	.580**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Academic Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.580**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

Table 4 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .580$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Since the r-value is significant with $p < .05$, therefore the null hypothesis four is rejected. Hence, there is a significant relationship between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. The result of this finding could be that the more senior secondary school students are conscious of their internal picture, they more their academic adjustment and higher academic performance.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant relationship between self-Acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

Table 5: PPMC Analysis (r) of the Relationship between Self-Acceptance and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

		Self-Acceptance	Academic Adjustment
Self-Acceptance	Pearson Correlation	1	.693**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Academic Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.693**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

Table 5 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .693$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Since the r-value is significant with $p < .05$, therefore the null hypothesis five is rejected. Hence, there is a significant relationship between self-acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. The result could mean that the more students accept who they are, the more their academic adjustment and academic performance.

Hypothesis Six: There is no significant relationship between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.

Table 6: PPMC Analysis (r) of the Relationship between Self-Respect and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

		Self-Respect	Academic Adjustment
Self-Respect	Pearson Correlation	1	.718**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Academic Adjustment	Pearson Correlation	.718**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .718$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Since the r-value is significant with $p < .05$, therefore the null hypothesis five is rejected. Hence, there is a significant relationship between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result implies that the more students attach dignity to their academics, the more their academic adjustment and better academic performance among senior secondary school students.

Summary of Findings

- There is a significant positive relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.
- There is a significant positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.
- There is a significant relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.
- There is a significant positive relationship between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State.
- There is a significant positive relationship between self-acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State
- There is a significant positive relationship between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State

Discussion of Findings

Adversity Awareness and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students

Table 1 revealed that the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .647$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Hence, there is a significant

positive relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result revealed the respondents' agreement that to a high extent, adversity awareness relates to academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. Thus, the higher the knowledge of the existence of adversity, the higher the likelihood of students' academic adjustment.

The present finding is in agreement with the finding of Feinberg et al. (2015) that there was a significant positive relationship between adversity awareness (emotional intelligence) and scholastic adjustment. The study found that the ability of students to be aware of their challenges significantly manage their adversity and adjust to their school environment. The finding of this current study is in line with the finding of Salguero et al. (2014) there was a significant positive relationship between perceived adversity awareness and academic adjustment among secondary school students. There was also a significant positive correlation between adversity and academic performance, indicating that female students had higher adversity intelligence levels than their male counterparts. Similarly, the finding of this present study is consistent with the finding of Odekunmi (2016) who found that there was significant positive relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment among students.

This finding is not surprising because adversity awareness will help the students to master his/her emotions and navigate through academic challenges to achieve higher academic performance.

Adversity Management and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students

Table 2 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .742$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Hence, there is a significant positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result revealed the respondents' agreement that to a high extent, adversity management relate to academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. The more the senior secondary school students know how to manage their adversity, the more they experience higher academic adjustment and academic performance.

The finding of the present study is in agreement with the finding of Ortiz (2022) that there was a significant positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment among college students. The finding of the present study is corroborated with the finding of Dubik et al. (2022) that there was a significant positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment.

This finding is true because adversity management will provide students with skills to handle school challenges effectively and achieve academic adjustment.

Self-Awareness and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students

Table 3 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .413$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Hence, there is a significant positive relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result revealed the respondents' agreement that to a high extent, self-awareness relate to academic adjustment of senior

secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. The implication of this result is that increase in self-awareness among senior secondary school students relates to academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. The finding of the present study is in agreement with the finding of Domenico and Jones (2017) that there was a strong significant relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment secondary school students. The finding of this study is consistent with the finding of Ojo and Asebiomo (2019) who found that self-acceptance was positively correlated with academic adjustment. This finding is not surprising because the more students are aware of them and their challenges, the more they adjust to their school work.

Self-Image and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students

Table 4 shows that the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .580$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Hence, there is a significant positive relationship between self-image and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result revealed the respondents' agreement that to a high extent, self-image relates to academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This could be true because students with positive self-image can withstand negative pressure and adjust themselves to their academic environment properly.

The finding of the present study is in agreement with the finding of Ratelle (2017) that self-concept (self-image) in the students of the higher primary stage were high. And social adjustment was high. The results showed also that there was a positive statistical relationship between self-image and school adjustment. The finding of this current study is also in accord with the finding of Aliero (2018) that there was a significant difference between parental socio-economic status and academic achievement of students. The study found that there was a significant relationship between self-image and academic adjustment of students. The finding of this current study is also in accord with the finding of Gasa et al (2019) that there was no significant relationship between self-image and socio-economic status of students. The study found that school adjustment was not influenced by self-image and socio-economic background. This finding is true because good self-image will help students to evaluate challenges, matching them by their strengths and weaknesses. This will help them to adjust adequately to their school environment and perform higher in their academics.

Self-Acceptance and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students

Table 5 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .693$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Hence, there is a significant positive relationship between self-acceptance and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result revealed the respondents' agreement that to a high extent, self-acceptance relates to academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. The implication of this result is that increase in self-acceptance tends to increase academic adjustment of senior secondary school students.

The finding of the present study is in agreement with the finding of Reddy (2017) that there was a significant difference between boys and girls in self-acceptance and school adjustment. The study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between self-acceptance and school adjustment. Similarly, the finding of this present study is also consistent with the

finding of Cooley and Unger (2019) that self-acceptance had a significant influence on students' academic adjustment. This finding is not surprising because students who accept themselves are well empowered to handle adversity with a positive mindset.

Self-Respect and Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students

Table 6 shows that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students is $r = .718$. This implies that there is a strong and positive relationship between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students. Hence, there is a significant positive relationship between self-respect and academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. This result revealed the respondents' agreement that to a high extent, self-respect relates to academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers State. The implication of this result is that students should have a strong feeling of pride in going to school and adjust properly in order to achieve higher academic performance. The finding of the present study is in agreement with the finding of Goni and Bello (2016) that there was a significant positive relationship between self-respect and school adjustment. The finding of the present study is consistent with the finding of Li et al (2020) they found that there was a significant positive relationship between socio-economic status and self-concept. The study found that both were significantly associated to self-respect and school adjustment, and academic achievement of students in mathematics. This finding is not surprising because students who respect themselves will avoid being used to cause trouble within the school and community.

Conclusion

The study investigated adversity intelligence and self-esteem as correlates of academic adjustment among senior secondary school students in East Senatorial District of Rivers State, Nigeria. However, the findings of the study indicated that there was a strong positive relationship between adversity awareness and academic adjustment among public senior secondary schools, that there was a significant positive relationship between adversity management and academic adjustment among public senior secondary schools, that there was a significant positive relationship between self-awareness and academic adjustment among public senior secondary schools, that there was a significant positive relationship between self-image and academic adjustment among public senior secondary schools, that there was a significant positive relationship between self-acceptance and academic adjustment among public senior secondary schools and there was a significant positive relationship between self-respect and academic adjustment among public senior secondary schools in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State. As such, steps ought to be taken to help students recognize adversity, build strategies to effectively manage adversity, develop good self-image, self-acceptance and self-respect. School counsellors should help students with low self-esteem through individual and group counselling, and through guidance programmes to enable these students to effectively navigate periods of adversity and ensure adequate academic adjustment which will ultimately boost the academic performance among public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- Counsellors, parents and teachers should help students with skills to identify what constitute adversity within their homes, school and society through guidance programmes, parental involvement and school rules and regulations respectively.
- School guidance counsellors should develop and teach adversity management strategies that will help students to effectively navigate periods of adversity

successfully to ensure adequate academic adjustment and higher academic performance.

- Parents and teachers should help students to become more self-conscious of what is happening within their school environment and to know what to do to avoid problems, how to avoid negative peer pressure so as to achieve higher academic performance.
- School counsellors and parents should help students to develop good self-image. This will help students to be able to withstand unnecessary pressures, increase their self-worth that will enable students to navigate times of adversity, achieve higher academic adjustment and academic performance.
- School counsellors, parents and teachers should provide emotional support that will help students to increase their self-acceptance (self-love, development of a growth mindset, self-appreciation, etc.) which could boost their academic adjustment and academic performance.
- Parents and teachers should help students to have a feeling of pride, dignity and worthiness as this will enhance confidence and self-respect. This will enable students to face adversity with high sense of overcoming all challenges.

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